

Synthesis of Quinazoline Derivatives Possessing Hypotensive and Antihistaminic Properties

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Several ethers and amines have been prepared by condensing 4-chloro quinazoline with different *N*-Substituted amino ethanols and *N*-Substituted ethylene diamines. The oxalate salts of these compounds were prepared and tested for their hypotensive and antihistaminic activities.

It is well known that *N*-Substituted amino ethyl ethers^{1a} $R-O-CH_2-CH_2-N$ and *N-N* substituted ethylene diamines possess hypotensive^{1a} activity on account of their adrenergic & ganglion blocking actions. At the same time since their chemical structures satisfy the structural requirements for antihistaminic property

viz. $-X-CH_2-CH_2-N$ $X=O$ or N they

exhibit the above property. In view of the observations of Deshpande and Kanwal Nain² on quinoline-4-amines and quinoline-4-ethers which were shown to possess both these properties, the present authors thought of extending the studies to a series of quinazoline ethers (1) and quinazoline-4-amines (2).

Pharmacology: These compounds showed appreciable hypotensive activity when studied on the blood pressure of anaesthetised dog and the following Table 1

gives the percentage fall in blood pressure. Compounds 2 and 7 showed remarkable fall in blood pressure in the preliminary screening. These compounds were also tested for antihistaminic activity on guinea pig-ileum preparation by the usual technique and were found to possess appreciable activity.

Experimental :

All these substances were obtained by the condensation of 4-chloro quinazoline³ (3) and the following *N*-Substituted ethanols and ethylene diamines.

N-Substituted amino ethanols.

- | | |
|---|------------------------|
| 1. 2-Piperidino ethanol ⁴ | B.P 196°-98° |
| 2. 2-Morpholino ethanol ⁵ | B.P 116°-19°/21-23 mm. |
| 3. 2-Pyrrolidino ethanol ⁶ | B.P 73°-75°/11 mm. |
| 4. 2- <i>o</i> -Toluidino ethanol ⁷ | B.P 144°-46°/7 mm. |
| 5. 2- <i>m</i> -Toluidino ethanol ⁸ | B.P 156°-59°/10 mm. |
| 6. 2- <i>p</i> -Toluidino ethanol ⁹ | B.P 155°-57°/8 mm. |
| 7. 2- <i>N-N</i> -dimethylamino ethanol ¹⁰ | B.P 131°-135° |
| 8. 2- <i>N</i> -Ethyl- <i>N</i> -phenyl amino ethanol ¹¹ | B.P 165°-67°/22 mm. |
| 9. <i>N</i> -Substituted ethylene diamines | |
| 10. 2-Piperidino ethyl amine ¹² | B.P 138°-84° |

4-(2-Piperidino ethoxy)quinazoline: The general procedure employed for synthesising quinazoline-4-ethers is illustrated by the preparation of the above

TABLE 1—COMPOUNDS POSSESSING HYPOTENSIVE ACTIVITY

S.No.	Name of compound	Dose	Actual fall in B.P.	%Fall
1.	4-(2- <i>N-N</i> Dimethyl amino ethoxy) quinazoline	3 mg/kg	25 mm	22
2.	4-(2-Piperidino ethoxy) quinazoline	3 mg/kg	55 mm	50
3.	4-(2-Piperidino ethyl amino) quinazoline	2 mg/kg	15	15
4.	4-(2- <i>o</i> -Toluidino ethoxy) quinazoline	2 mg/kg	25	23
5.	4-(2- <i>m</i> -Toluidino ethoxy) quinazoline	3 mg/kg	No effect	
6.	4-(2-Pyrrolidino ethoxy) quinazoline	2 mg/kg	(20 mm rise in B.P)	+20
7.	4-(2- <i>N</i> -Methyl <i>N</i> -phenyl ethoxy) quinazoline	3 mg/kg	60 mm	54
8.	4-(2-Morpholino ethoxy) quinazoline	3 mg/kg	No effect	

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TABLE 2

S.No.	Compound	M.P °C	Formula	%Carbon		%Hydrogen	
				Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	4-2(Piperidino) ethoxy quinazoline (mono oxalate)	234-35	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₅	—	—	—	—
2.	4-2(morpholine) ethoxy quinazoline (mono oxalate)	237-38	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	55.21	55.01	5.55	5.44
3.	4-2(pyrrolidino) ethoxy quinazoline (mono oxalate)	215-16	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₅	54.92	54.70	5.76	5.99
4.	4-2(o-Toluidino) ethoxy quinazoline	113-14	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	72.85	73.12	6.21	6.02
5.	4-2(m-Toluidino) ethoxy quinazoline	103-104	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	72.93	73.12	6.03	6.02
6.	4-2(p-Toluidino) ethoxy quinazoline	127-28	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	73.81	73.12	6.40	6.02
7.	4-2(NN dimethyl) ethoxy quinazoline-mono oxalate	207-208	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	54.45	54.72	5.70	5.54
8.	4-2-(Piperidino) ethyl amino quinazoline	218-19	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄	59.07	58.96	6.33	6.35

compound. Alkoxide of 2-piperidino ethanol was prepared in the usual manner by treating in a 100 ml round bottomed flask 0.53 g (0.022 mols) of sodium with 3 g (0.02 mols) of 2-piperidino ethanol. 3 g (0.022 mols) of 4-chloro quinazoline was then added and the mixture heated at 80°C for 10 hours in dry benzene. 20-30 ml of water was added to the cooled reaction product followed by acidification with dil HCl. The aqueous layer was separated and the benzene layer was washed with water twice (2×20 ml). The combined aqueous extract was basified by sodium hydroxide solution with external cooling and the liberated base was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and the solvent removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The residue was distilled under reduced pressure and the pure base was obtained as a colourless oil. A portion of the base was converted into its oxalate salt which was recrystallized from alcohol, colourless needles m. p. 234°-35°. (Found : N, 12.58% Calc for C₁₇H₂₁N₃O₅; N, 12.11%). The various ethers prepared are listed in Table 2.

Quinazoline-4-amines (2): Vide Table (2) 3 g (0.02 mols) of 4 chloro quinazoline was dissolved in 5.0 g (0.053 mols) of phenol by washing in a 100 ml round bottomed flask fitted with a reflux condenser and the mixture was heated in an oil bath maintained at 110°. Substituted ethylene diamine (0.03 moles) (Vide supra) was gradually added at this temperature. The mixture was then raised to 140°-45° at which it was maintained for 8 hrs. The reaction mixture was diluted with benzene and acidified with dil HCl. The acid layer was removed and the benzene layer washed with water. The combined

acid extract and water washings were basified with sodium hydroxide solution and the liberated base was extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried and after removal of the solvent, the base was converted into its oxalate salt and crystallised from alcohol.

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